

European Research Infrastructure supporting Smart Grid and Smart Energy Systems Research, Technology Development, Validation and Roll Out – Second Edition

Work Package WP3

NA2 - Dissemination, Communication, and Collaboration

Deliverable D3.5

D-NA2.3a Summary Report on Trans-national Access Calls

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List of Abbreviations

COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease 2019
DoA	Description of Action
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
MTR	Mid-Term Review
NA	Networking Activities
PoC	Person of Contact
RI	Research Infrastructure
RTD	Research and Technology Development
TA	Trans-national Access
USP	User Selection Panel
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Executive Summary

Reported in this document are the efforts of the ERIGrid 2.0 consortium for the dissemination of the Trans-national Access (TA) in the time frame from 1 April 2020 until 31 March 2022, as well as the outcome of these efforts for TA Calls 1-4 and with Call 5 ongoing.

In particular, the materials and channels used for TA dissemination are documented, with examples of undertaken activities. These include the project website, social media channels, the newsletter, and presentation slides.

Besides the dissemination activities undertaken in Work Package (WP)3-Networking Activities (NA)2 led by DERlab as Work Package Leader (WPL), the report contains a brief overview of other partners' activities for the dissemination of ERIGrid 2.0's TA programme.

Finally, the numbers of reached TA proposals for each call and the success rate of the used dissemination channels are documented. Based on this information, conclusions regarding the effectiveness of each channel are drawn. The report concludes with the lessons learned and the subsequent measures in terms of further TA promotion, based on the progress to date and the goals established.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

This document is the first summary report on TA dissemination activities of the ERIGrid 2.0 project. It presents a summary of the efforts for promotion of TA opportunities undertaken by DERlab as the WPL as well as the rest of the members of the consortium. Furthermore, the deliverable documents the marketing materials and channels that have been developed for this dissemination.

Within its TAs ERIGrid 2.0 offers external users free access to the Research Infrastructures (RIs) of the consortium partners, including funding for travel expenses, accommodation, subsistence costs, as well as scientific and dissemination support. The target audience to benefit from this offer comes from research, academia and industry in the domains of power system testing, smart grids and energy systems. Research projects in compliance with European Research and Technology Developments (RTDs) priorities and with the prospect of social impact and impact on European Union (EU) industry are supported. The TA programme aims to support new smart energy solutions and the development of an integrated European RI (*ERIGrid 2.0 Grant Agreement*, 2019).

Having established a set of channels and a significant following on each of them in the predecessor project ERIGrid, ERIGrid 2.0 decided to continue using these accounts in the new project after necessary re-adjustment and re-branding. This way the consortium ensures the transfer of best practices between the projects, maintaining momentum for the benefit of reaching the target audience.

Furthermore, it was decided in the consortium to use the term “Lab Access” for public promotion outside the project, as it is considered to be more comprehensive than the term “TA” for project-external persons.

In light of Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19), the consortium made an effort to adapt to the situation and accommodate the TA offer, abide by health and safety regulations. Host laboratories strived to offer remote access as an alternative where possible, generally attempting to offer the maximum possible flexibility to TA applicants and users.

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document is organised as follows: Section 1 provides information about the report content. Section 2 introduces the timeline for the TA calls. Section 3 presents materials and channels established for the promotion and how they were used so far. Section 4 provides an overview of activities performed by consortium members. Section 5 presents the outcomes of the activities. The report is concluded in Section 6. Finally, images of the developed and used dissemination and marketing material are provided in the Appendix A: Project Website, Appendix B: Example of a Lab Access Page, Appendix C: Project Flyer, Appendix D: 1st Project Newsletter, Appendix E: LinkedIn Sponsored Campaign, and Appendix F: Lab Access Slide.

2 Lab Access Calls Timeline

The ERIGrid 2.0 TA programme is organised into three-month time windows, during which external users can submit their applications for lab access. The calls are launched every four months, with one calendar month reserved between the closing date of the previous call and the opening date of the next call.

The current report covers the time frame of the following TA calls and therefore presents the dissemination efforts made during and between these:

- Call 1: 1 October 2020 – 31 December 2020
- Call 2: 1 February 2021 – 30 April 2021
- Call 3: 1 June 2021 – 31 August 2021
- Call 4: 1 October 2021 – 31 December 2021
- Call 5: 1 February 2022 – 30 April 2022

3 Lab Access Dissemination Material and Channels

This section describes materials and channels that ERIGrid 2.0 has established as tools for promotion of TA opportunities: the project website, the project flyer, the newsletter, the representation on social networks, and the presentation slides.

3.1 Project Website

The project website, available at <https://erigrd2.eu> is the main platform for all public information about ERIGrid 2.0, its activities and outcomes. Correspondingly, the TA programme is provided an extensive exposure on the website. A dedicated elaborated subpage <https://erigrd2.eu/lab-access> was set up providing all necessary details about the TA programme in a comprehensive and popularised way (see Appendix A: Project Website). The consortium made the effort to provide as much guidance to potential applicants as possible. In particular, the page presents the following details valuable for potential applicants:

- General information about the TA, its target audience and what kind of support the programme offers
- Timeline of the past and closely upcoming TA calls
- Complete overview of the available facilities, with the option to filter them out according to one of the categories: "Transient Power System Dynamics and Control Validation" or "Smart Energy Systems Integration and Validation"
- Step-by-step instructions on how potential users can submit their applications
- Selection criteria
- Relevant documents or necessary templates: lab access guide, proposal template, link to the proposal submission platform, contract model, test canvas template, and report template
- FAQ section, regularly updated based on the ongoing communication with applicants

At the time of writing the TA subpage gathered over 32,000 pageviews since the project start.

Figure 1: Pageviews of the TA subpage

Each of the available facilities in the overview on this page is linked to an individual page with detailed information about the RI provided at the corresponding facility, offered services, lab access conditions and any further relevant details, including videos and pictures. Furthermore,

each lab page contains a contact form designed for any arising questions from potential applicants. The submitted forms are sent automatically directly to the Person of Contact (PoC) of the corresponding labs. An example of a lab page is given in Appendix B: Example of a Lab Access Page.

Furthermore, relevant for the TA and cross-linked from the TA subpage are the following two subpages:

- "*User Projects*"¹ presenting the list of implemented TA user projects
- "*Selection Panel*"² presenting the list of the User Selection Panel (USP) members for the purposes of transparency and for applicants to be able to indicate possible conflicts of interest in their applications

Upon completion of an ever growing number of user projects, the consortium will set up a dedicated subpage "Success Stories" to showcase successful examples of TA user research. This measure will contribute to the dissemination of the results as set out in the Grant Agreement (GA) (*ERIGrid 2.0 Grant Agreement*, 2019) and to attract new potential TA users.

3.2 Flyer

It was decided to include the information on the TA in the project flyer (see Appendix C: Project Flyer) to make sure this opportunity is advertised along with other project aspects. Therefore, the project flyer contains initial information on the TA programme, indicating general information, application timeline and reference to further details. As the most easy to handle promotion material, the flyer is designed to be widely used for dissemination at any occasions, such as events like conferences and trade fairs, meetings and personal networking.

3.3 Newsletter

At the time of writing, the project has 600 persons on the newsletter subscribers list. Seven newsletters have been released to date, out of which six advertised TA and corresponding calls. The average open rate across the newsletters varies from 31.5% to 38.7%, which is considered a good rate for newsletters as a dissemination channel. An example of the first newsletter dedicated solely to the launch of the first TA call on 1 October 2020 is shown in Appendix D: 1st Project Newsletter.

3.4 Social Networks

ERIGrid 2.0 uses social networks *LinkedIn*³ and *Twitter*⁴ in general project promotion and TA dissemination.

At the time of writing, ERIGrid 2.0 has over 1,400 followers on LinkedIn and nearly 500 followers on Twitter. All five past calls were advertised extensively, including:

- Announcements of the opening calls (Figure 2)

¹<https://erigrd2.eu/user-projects/>

²<https://erigrd2.eu/selection-panel/>

³<https://www.linkedin.com/company/erigrd-project/>

⁴<https://twitter.com/ERIGrid>

- Three sponsored campaigns on LinkedIn, which collectively gathered over 80,000 impressions and over 300 clicks through to the TA subpage (see Appendix E: LinkedIn Sponsored Campaign)
- Regular updates highlighting the RI of each facility

Figure 2: Example of the call announcement on LinkedIn

Examples of TA updates on Twitter and the reached engagement are presented in Figure 3 and Figure 4.

Figure 3: Example of TA updates on Twitter

Figure 4: Example of exposure on Twitter during 4th TA call

3.5 Presentation Slides

The general project presentation is designed for project dissemination by the project consortium at any relevant event and occasion. The presentation contains a slide highlighting the TA programme, including the map of available facilities, their logos and reference for further details. Inclusion of the TA programme in the presentation ensures it is provided necessary exposure as project partners are participating in a number of events on an ongoing basis where the ERIGrid 2.0 target audience is present.

4 Consortium's Dissemination of Lab Access Calls

Table 1 presents an overview of dissemination efforts undertaken by consortium members.

Table 1: Overview of the consortium's dissemination efforts.

Partner	Type of Activity	Event, Platform, Channel	Location, Time	Type, Size of Audience
DERlab	Updates and posts	Social media channels (LinkedIn, Twitter)	Regular and ongoing	Research, academia, industry; ca. 1,800 followers
DERlab	Email promotion	Email	During TA calls	Research; broad international networks (ISGAN Annex 5 SIRFN, ETIP SNET, EERA JP Smart Grids, BRIDGE)
OFFIS	Updates and posts	Social Media Channel LinkedIn	During TA Calls, after TA completion at the SESA laboratory	Research institutes, universities, companies ca. 700 followers
CRES	Updates and posts	Organisation's website	During TA calls	Research institutes, universities, companies
CRES	Email promotion	Email	During TA calls	Research institutes, universities, companies, including the consortium of GIFT (H2020)
JRC	Email promotion	Email	Regular and ongoing	European research institutions and private companies operating in the energy sector
VTT	Updates and posts	Social Media (LinkedIn), Organisation's website	During TA calls	Research institutes, universities, companies
AIT	Updates and posts	Social Media (LinkedIn), Organisation's website, AIT Social Media Channel	During TA calls, posts during lab access	Research institutes, universities, personal contacts, companies
AIT	Email promotion	Email	Regular and ongoing	Research institutes, universities, companies, personal contacts
AIT	Workshops, Tutorials, Webinars, Fairs	Presentation	DigiSect 2022, OSM-SES 2022, DERlab GA, CIGRE Session 2022, IEEE SMC 2022, IRED 2022, RICH Europe Webinar, IEA ISGAN-SIRFN Meetings	Research institutes, universities, companies
ICCS	Email promotion	Email	Regular and ongoing	Research institutes, universities, companies, personal contacts

Partner	Type of Activity	Event, Platform, Channel	Location, Time	Type, Size of Audience
ICCS	Updates and posts	Social Media Channel LinkedIn, Organisation's website	During TA calls, posts after TA completion	Research institutes, universities, personal contacts, companies
ICCS	Seminars, Panel Sessions, Tutorials	Presentation	IES Egypt, PES ISGT Europe, University of Seville	Research institutes, universities, companies
RSE	Updates and posts	Social Media Channels, LinkedIn	During TA calls	Research institutes, universities, personal contacts, companies

5 Outcomes of Lab Access Calls Dissemination

In four TA calls to date the consortium received 43 proposals. Based on preliminary estimations that number amounts to approximately 34% of access days set out as an objective in the Description of Action (DoA). Having completed four calls and with the fifth call running at the time of writing, the consortium foresees another five calls until the project end, with 10 calls overall in the duration of the project. Assuming the consortium keeps up the rate of received TA proposals, the target of access days can be achieved.

The DoA set out the goal of at least 25% of the executed user projects must be carried out with industry participation. The progress estimation upon completion of the first four calls lies at approximately 13%.

For effective dissemination of TA calls it is important for the consortium to know which of the used promotion channels result in the most outcomes in terms of numbers of submitted proposals in each call. For that purpose, the questions about how the applicants had learned about the TA was included in the TA application procedure. The collected answers are summarised in Table 2, which presents the outcomes of dissemination through specific channels. It is frequent that the applicants indicate multiple sources of their initial knowledge of ERIGrid 2.0, therefore the numbers of proposals for all sources indicated for a specific call may collectively exceed the number of actual proposals received in the call.

Table 2: Outcomes of promotion through channels

	1st call 11 proposals	2nd call 13 proposals	3rd call 3 proposals	4th call 16 proposals
Personal recommendation by ERIGrid 2.0 partner	3	5	3	7
Previous connection with ERIGrid	1	4	-	3
Website	3	-	-	3
Social media	1	2	2	1
Involved in ERIGrid 2.0	-	1	-	4
Project partner email promotion	2	-	1	-
Event	1	-	-	1
PowerGlobe Forum	1	1	-	-
Newsletter	1	-	-	-

It is noted from the collected answers that the highest number of proposals collectively for all four calls to date as well as for each call came through as a result of personal recommendation and personal promotion by an ERIGrid 2.0 partner. The second most effective source proved to be past knowledge of the predecessor project ERIGrid, including past TA users in ERIGrid, past consortium members and others. Following are social media and the project website as sources of TA information.

6 Conclusions

Based on the outcomes of the previous TA calls, the most successful means of obtaining proposals proved to be individual partners' promotion and personal recommendations to potential applicants. Therefore, the consortium will emphasise this channel in the further promotion. With more ERIGrid 2.0 events being organised further on in the project, the partners will have suitable occasions for such networking activities.

Furthermore, according to the recommendations resulting from the Mid-Term Review (MTR) of the ERIGrid 2.0 project (02/02/2022), in the future, a strong focus should be put on the general dissemination of the work and on the promotion of the access to the lab facilities, beyond the project partners and their surrounding research communities. At the time of writing, the social media analytics outlines that the largest part of ERIGrid 2.0 audiences comes indeed from research and academia (Figure 5). Thus the project will strive to engage a wider audience, also trying to address interest groups in the general public arena or policymakers and increase its outreach to industrial groups. This will allow the project consortium to further expand and develop the full potential of the project impact.

Figure 5: ERIGrid 2.0 followers by organization type

In order to especially attract the attention of the audience beyond academia and already connected research communities, the consortium will in particular increase its social media storytelling activities, dissemination of the already completed TA project results, and formulating added value messages for industry and policy groups.

It is a known fact that the dissemination of the lab access opportunities will be more successful and the offered services will get more feedback and interest once the pandemic is over, but the preparation for these additional interactions has already started.

References

ERIGrid 2.0 Grant Agreement. (2019). European Commission.

Appendix A: Project Website

GET FREE ACCESS TO LEADING SMART GRID AND ENERGY SYSTEMS LABS AND SERVICES

ERIGrid 2.0 invites all interested engineers involved in the domains of power system testing, smart grids and energy systems to receive free funding to access the best laboratories of Europe and perform their own experimental research. There are two kinds of lab access services available in ERIGrid 2.0:

FREE ACCESS TO 21 PHYSICAL LABS

Physical free access to our laboratories can be performed on-site at the location of the lab or remotely if the infrastructure allows. To get this access you need to apply as described below and to be selected by the independent User Selection Panel (USP).

If your application is successful, you will receive funding for your research stay at the location of the laboratory you selected, completely covering the following expenses:

- Travelling
- Accommodation
- All lab operation costs and physical lab access to ERIGrid 2.0 testing and simulation facilities
- Access to concentrated know-how and best practices in the field of smart grid and energy systems, such as: power system components characterisation and evaluation, smart grid ICT / automation validation, co-simulation, real-time simulation and Power/Controller Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL), and others.

APPLY NOW UNTIL 30 APRIL 2022!

Please note that applications close automatically on the date of the deadline, and no late applications can be accepted.

Schedule of calls for lab access proposals:

- 1st call: 1 October 2020 – 31 December 2020 (closed)
- 2nd call: 1 February 2021 – 30 April 2021 (closed)
- 3rd call: 1 June 2021 – 31 August 2021 (closed)
- 4th call: 1 October 2021 – 31 December 2021 (closed)
- 5th call: **1 February 2022 – 30 April 2022 (open)**
- 6th call: 1 June 2022 – 31 August 2022

Further calls for physical lab access will be open/closing regularly on a 4 months basis.

FREE ACCESS TO 9 VIRTUAL FACILITIES

The access to the virtual facilities requires no specific application and user proposals are not submitted to a selection process.

You can access and start using the free virtual services right away taking the following points into account:

- The provided virtual data, services and resources are openly and freely available under open access licenses through communication networks.
- Access to virtual services allows for a quick, easy and casual access to existing virtual resources by eliminating administrative obstacles.
- Users can try the provided virtual services without obligations.
- No individual support or supervision is offered to the users.

PHYSICAL LAB ACCESS APPLICATION PROCESS

Identify your experimental needs: empirical topic and testing/validation goals

Select potential labs (up to 3) which are suitable for your topic

Build up your team or decide to apply as an individual user

Write the proposal using this template

Your proposal will be evaluated by independent reviewers from this list – Please point out any names that may involve a conflict of interest in the proposal submission system

Register yourself in the proposal submission system and submit your proposal - list all user group members in the submission system (same list as in the proposal)

ERIGrid 2.0 partners offer a wide range of installations and competences to assist successful applicants with conducting experiments. Such a common framework of applied smart grid expertise will accelerate the development of an integrated pan-European research infrastructure.

- Lab Access Guide
- Proposal Templates
- Proposal Submission
- Contract Model
- Test Canvas Templates
- Report Templates

PHYSICAL LAB ACCESS SELECTION CRITERIA

Your proposal for physical lab access must meet the following criteria:

- Scientific and technical relevance, originality and innovation, methodology, robust and realistic test/evaluation approach
- Prospect of knowledge enhancement at the research infrastructures
- Completeness and organization of the proposal, clear definition of the objectives and expected results, relevance of the proposed dissemination actions, justified amount of requested access
- Compliance with European RTD policies and priorities; prospect of social impact and impact on EU industry. New users, young researchers, female researchers are especially welcome.

The evaluation will be performed by the User Selection Panel, an international independent group of experts with diverse profiles (academia, industry) covering the different domains of the smart energy systems (power systems, ICT, etc.). In parallel, a technical and economic feasibility check for the potential lab implementation will be done by the addressed ERIGrid 2.0 infrastructures.

PHYSICAL LAB ACCESS FAQ

- WHAT IS A "USER GROUP" AND HOW MANY PERSONS CAN BE PART OF IT?

Applications are submitted by User Groups (UG). A UG is a team of one or more researchers from one or more institutions/companies which is led by a so-called user group leader. Despite the fact that the user group implementing the project in the lab is normally composed by two researchers, one single researcher is also allowed. Unless fully justified, the maximum number must be always kept to three researchers getting access to the lab.
- WHAT IS THE TYPICAL DURATION OF A PHYSICAL LAB ACCESS USER PROJECT?
- DO THE APPLICANT(S) NEED TO CONTACT THE PREFERRED LAB DURING THE PROPOSAL PREPARATION?
- CAN I APPLY FOR A LAB LOCATED IN MY COUNTRY?
- CAN UK USER GROUPS STILL APPLY?
- CAN NON EU PROJECTS APPLY?
- PLAGIARISM CHECK OF PROPOSALS
- WHEN WILL I BE INFORMED IF MY PROPOSAL WAS APPROVED?
- WHAT SHOULD I DO IF MY PROPOSAL IS APPROVED?
- WILL A CONTRACT TEMPLATE BE MADE AVAILABLE?
- WILL I HAVE TO PUBLICISE THE RESULTS OF MY PROJECT?
- WHAT HAPPENS AFTER THE ACCESS?
- ARE THERE ANY EXAMPLES OF PERFORMED USER PROJECTS?
- HOW DOES COVID-19 PANDEMIC INFLUENCE THE LAB ACCESS PROGRAMME?
- IS IT STILL HAVE SOME QUESTIONS, HOW CAN I CONTACT YOU?

PHYSICAL LABS AND VIRTUAL SERVICES

Access to physical labs can be on-site or remote, depending on the conditions of specific laboratories. To know if remote access can be organised in your case, please contact the laboratory staff through corresponding subpages below.

ALL	ON-SITE AND DEBATE TRANSIENT POWER SYSTEM DYNAMICS AND CONTROL VALIDATION	ON-SITE AND REMOTE SMART ENERGY SYSTEMS INTEGRATION AND VALIDATION	VIRTUAL FACILITIES

Appendix B: Example of a Lab Access Page

REAL-TIME LAB (RWTH AACHEN UNIVERSITY)

The RWTH-ACS Real-time Lab is located in the E.ON Energy Research Center and operated by the Institute for Automation of Complex Power Systems (ACS). As part of the E.ON Energy Research Center (E.ON ERC), ACS is one of four Institutes out of three faculties of the RWTH Aachen University. The E.ON ERC is the result of a public-private partnership between industry and the scientific community.

As one of the largest energy companies in Europe, E.ON SE has come together with the internationally renowned RWTH Aachen University in order to realize this unique project. The E.ON ERC is located in the Sustainable Energy Cluster in the RWTH Campus.

Location: Aachen, Germany
www.acs.eonerc.rwth-aachen.de

- [+ DESCRIPTION OF THE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE](#)

- [+ SERVICES OFFERED](#)

- [+ DESCRIPTION OF THE ORGANIZATION](#)

- [+ LAB ACCESS CONDITIONS OFFERED BY RWTH AACHEN](#)

Do you have questions left? Feel free to contact us below.
 If your enquiry contains strictly confidential information, please leave your contact details below and the lab host will contact you personally.

Name *

Email *

Message *

Ich bin kein Roboter.

reCAPTCHA
 Datenschutzerklärung • Nutzungsbedingungen

Appendix C: Project Flyer

FREE PHYSICAL AND VIRTUAL LAB ACCESS

The ERIGrid 2.0 project invites all interested engineers in the domains of power system testing, smart grids and smart energy to receive free funding to access the best laboratories and services of Europe for their own experimental research. Physical lab access can be organised either on-site or remotely. Furthermore, ERIGrid 2.0 provides virtual access to 8 facilities and services without applications required.

USERS WILL RECEIVE:

- on-site or remote access to 21 first-class laboratories or application-free virtual access to 8 services of ERIGrid partners
- in case of physical access: funding for their complete research stay at the location of the selected laboratory, including coverage of expenses for travelling, accommodation and lab operation costs
- access to concentrated know-how and best practices in the field of smart grids and energy systems components characterisation and evaluation, smart grid ICT / automation validation, co-simulation, real-time simulation and Power/Controller Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL), and others
- opportunity to advance their own research and solutions
- working with the top smart grid and energy systems experts
- chance to impact EU industry
- promotion of their research through ERIGrid 2.0 channels

Find detailed descriptions of labs and services and all further details at erigrd2.eu/lab-access.

apply every 3 months for physical lab access

access virtual services anytime no application required

CONSORTIUM COORDINATED BY

CONNECTING EUROPEAN SMART GRID RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

FREE ACCESS TO EUROPE'S BEST SMART GRID AND ENERGY SYSTEMS LABS

@ERIGrid 2.0 Project

www.erigrd2.eu

Supported by the H2020 Programme under Contract No. 870620

Based on the results from the predecessor project ERIGrid-1, ERIGrid 2.0 will expand the research services and tools of research infrastructures for validating smart energy networks with the electric power grid as the main backbone.

ABOUT

- ERIGrid 2.0: European Research Infrastructure supporting Smart Grid and Smart Energy Systems Research, Technology Development, Validation and Roll Out – Second Edition
- 20 partners from research, academia and industry
- 21 first-class European labs provided to external users for free access on-site or remotely
- 8 facilities and services provided to external users for virtual access
- 13 European countries represented in the consortium
- Duration: 1 April 2020 – 30 September 2024
- Budget: €10M funded by the European Commission

GOALS

- support the research, technology development, and innovation of smart grid and smart energy systems approaches, concepts, and solutions in Europe taking a holistic and cyber-physical systems-based approach into account
- provide system-level support and education for industrial and academic researchers in power and energy systems research and technology development

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

- enhance system-level validation methods
- improve and extend tools to accommodate system-level tests over multiple test infrastructures and domains
- implement and demonstrate the developed concepts, methods, and tools into the research infrastructures (RI) of the ERIGrid 2.0 partners

NETWORKING OBJECTIVES

- knowledge-exchange with other European smart grid and smart energy systems RIs
- knowledge transfer between researchers, technicians, and RI managers
- Open Access (OA) provision of achievements and reinforced collaboration with industry and energy utilities
- education of power and energy system professionals
- international collaboration and harmonization

Appendix D: 1st Project Newsletter

Connecting European Smart Grid Infrastructures

European Research Infrastructure Supporting Smart Grid and Smart Energy Systems
Research, Technology Development, Validation and Roll out - Second Edition

APPLY FOR FREE LAB ACCESS
UNTIL 31 DECEMBER 2020

The ERIGrid 2.0 consortium invites applications for free lab access: successful candidates working in the domains of power system testing, smart grids and energy systems will be able to conduct their own experimental research free of charge at the ERIGrid 2.0 facilities.

Starting from October 2020 and up until 31 December 2020, applications are welcome for research stays and remote lab access to ERIGrid 2.0 testing facilities. Distributed over 13 European countries, 21 top-class laboratories will open doors to external users and their research projects. Successful applicants will be granted funding covering their travelling expenses, accommodation, all lab operation costs and support of the laboratory staff on site.

Among selection criteria are such factors as scientific and technical relevance and innovation, as well as prospect of social impact and impact on EU industry.

Providing open access to Europe's best laboratories, their equipment, know-how and experts' support – all free of charge, ERIGrid 2.0 lab access programme is a unique opportunity for smart energy engineers. With the first call closing on 31 December 2020, ERIGrid 2.0 will be inviting further applications on a 3-4-month basis.

Find all information about the laboratories and the application process on the [Lab Access page](#) and in the [Lab Access Guide](#)

Keep up with ERIGrid 2.0 news

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Appendix E: LinkedIn Sponsored Campaign

ERIGrid 2.0 Project
1,259 followers
2mo •

ERIGrid 2.0 Project

We're launching the 4th call for your Lab Access applications! Apply until 31 December 2021 for free-of-charge access to Europe's best smart energy testing facilities for your own research: <https://lnkd.in/evBCF9s>. For your research stay or remote access you can choose the laboratories of the following research centers: [AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH](#), [SINTEF Energy Research](#), [DTU - Technical University of Denmark](#), [Ormazabal](#), [University of Strathclyde](#), [PNDC](#), [ΔΕΔΔΗΕ A.E.](#), [HEDNO S.A.](#), [ICCS - NTUA](#), [Ricerca sul Sistema Energetico - RSE SpA](#), [OFFIS - Institute for Information Technology](#), [Fraunhofer IEE](#), [KEMA Labs](#), [RWTH Aachen University](#), [Centre for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving \(CRES\)](#), [Tecnalia Research & Innovation](#), [Technische Universiteit Delft](#), [JRC of the European Commission](#), [PV Technology](#), [FOSS Research Centre for Sustainable Energy](#), and [VTT](#). Remote access to the labs is possible depending on the conditions at the lab and your research requirements.

Photo: RWTH Aachen

#smartenergy #energysystem #powersupply #PowerSystems #SmartGrids #Validation #Testing #PowerSystemsLabValidation #hardwareintheLoop #SmartGridsValidationTesting #distributedenergy #laboratory #energysystemvalidation #energyengineering #renewableenergy #distributionnetworks #smartgridlaboratory #openaccess #horizon2020 #h2020project #EU #H2020 #gridtesting #gridintegration

FREE ACCESS TO SMART GRID AND ENERGY SYSTEMS LABS

Sponsored impressions: 28,449 Impressions

Sponsored stats ⓘ

Running on 1 campaign •

28,449	13	0.33%
Impressions	Reactions	Click-through rate
0	2	94
Comments	Shares	Clicks
0	1%	
Follows	Engagement rate	

Organic stats ⓘ

1,769	27	2.26%
Impressions	Reactions	Click-through rate
0	12	40
Comments	Shares	Clicks

Appendix F: Lab Access Slide

apply every 3 months for physical lab access

**access virtual services anytime
no application required**

<https://erigrd2.eu/lab-access/>

Consortium

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